

THE PROBLEM OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Urolbaeva Shokhsanam Odil kizi

**Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami Faculty of
Preschool Education 1st year master's student**

Annotation: This article discusses the problem of speech development in preschool children. Such concepts as: speech, speech development, language are disclosed. The tasks of speech development by different authors are also presented. The question of the importance of the formation of correct and good oral speech in preschool children has been studied.

Keywords: speech, speech development, language, speech development tasks.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of speech development of preschool children is very relevant today. The question of speech development was dealt with by many scientists and teachers.

A.G. Arushanova gives the following definition of speech: "This is the most important creative function of a person, the area of manifestation of the inherent ability of all people to cognition, self-organization, self-development, to build their personality, their inner world through dialogue with other personalities, other worlds, other cultures".

According to F.A. Sokhin, "Speech is a psychophysical process, it is the realization of a language that fulfills its communicative purpose only through speech".

The practical solution of speech development issues largely depends on understanding the relationship between language and speech. In everyday life, these

words are often used as synonyms, but this is wrong. The characteristic of speech is usually given through its opposition to language. "Language is a system of objectively existing, socially fixed signs that correlate conceptual content and typical sound, as well as a system of rules for their use and compatibility. Language is a means of communication, and speech is the process of communication itself. Language is abstract and reproducible, objective in relation to the speaker.

Speech is concrete and unique, material, consists of articulate signs perceived by the senses, dynamic, subjective, is a kind of free creative activity of the individual.

Speech development is considered as the formation of skills and abilities to accurately, expressively, freely and appropriately use language units, rules of speech etiquette. This is a purposeful, systematic and systematic process in which, under the guidance of a teacher, children master a certain range of speech skills and abilities.

Thus, the development of speech is closely connected with the development of personality, the development of consciousness, knowledge of the surrounding world. A preschool-age child has a growing experience of speech communication, and at the same time, a sense of language and the ability to create words are formed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The mastery of the native language, the development of speech is one of the most important acquisitions of a child in preschool childhood and is considered in modern preschool education as a common basis for the upbringing and education of children.

K.D.Ushinsky attached special importance to the sense of language, which, according to him, suggests to the child the way of combining words in a sentence, grammatical turnover, the place of stress in a word.

During the preschool period, contextual (abstract, generalized, devoid of

visual support) speech is gradually formed. Contextual speech appears first when a child retells fairy tales, stories, then when describing some events from his personal experience, his own experiences, impressions.

The actual task of speech development in the senior preschool age is the development of diction. It is known that the organs of the speech-motor apparatus are not yet coordinated and clearly functioning in children.

Some children are characterized by excessive haste, unclear digestion of words, "swallowing" endings. There is also another extreme: an unnecessarily slow, stretched manner of pronunciation of words. Special exercises help children overcome such difficulties, improve their diction.

The Russian psychological school believes that the development of a child's speech has a socio-historical conditionality.

L.S. Vygotsky put forward and developed the idea of the social nature of the causes and features of speech development, which was confirmed in the studies of P.Ya. Galperin, A.N. Leontiev, A.R. Luria, D.B. Elkonin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Many factors influence the successful development of a child's speech. One of these factors is interaction with a native speaker, who is a role model for him. Communication is formed, according to M.I.Lisina, by three main categories of means of communication.

1. subject-effective.
2. expressive and mimic.
3. speech operations.

In modern methodology, the goal of speech development of preschool children is the formation of not only correct, but also good oral speech, of course, taking into account their age characteristics and capabilities.

The general task of speech development consists of a number of particular,

special tasks.

The teacher's knowledge of the content of the tasks is of great methodological importance, since the correct organization of work on the development of speech and teaching the native language depends on it.

The tasks of speech development are reflected in the program, which determines the volume of speech skills and abilities, the speech requirements of children in different age groups.

F.A. Sokhin identifies the following speech tasks:

1. Dictionary development.

2. Familiarization with fiction, which is not speech in the proper sense of the word. Rather, it can be considered as a means of implementing all the tasks of the child's speech development and language acquisition in its aesthetic function. The artistic word has a huge impact on the upbringing of the individual, is a source and means of enriching the speech of children.

3. Education of the sound culture of speech is a multidimensional task, which includes more specific micro-tasks related to the development of perception of native speech sounds and pronunciation (speaking, speech pronunciation). It involves: the development of speech hearing, on the basis of which the perception and distinction of phonological means of language takes place; training in correct sound pronunciation; education of orthoepic correctness of speech; mastering the means of sound expressiveness of speech (tone of speech, timbre of voice, tempo, stress, strength of voice, intonation); the development of clear diction.

4. Development of coherent speech.

In the "Program of speech development of preschool children in kindergarten" under the guidance of O.S.Ushakova, the theoretical foundations and directions of work on the development of children's speech skills are revealed, aimed at the development of coherent speech of preschoolers. It contains the following tasks:

1. development of coherent speech.

2. development of the lexical side of speech.
3. formation of the grammatical structure of speech.
4. development of the sound side of speech.
5. development of figurative speech.

Each task is interconnected, and the leading role is the development of coherent speech.

E.I.Tikheeva identifies the following tasks of speech development:

In working with children, the tasks of speech development are conditional, they are also closely related. When enriching the vocabulary of children, at the same time it is necessary to take into account the correct use of words, their clear pronunciation, contribute to the formation of coherent speech. The interrelation of different speech tasks on the basis of an integrated approach to their solution creates prerequisites for the most effective development of speech skills and abilities.

From age to age, there is a gradual complication of each task, learning methods change. According to O.S.Ushakova, the educator should be presented with the main lines of succession of speech development tasks that are solved in the previous and subsequent age group, and the complex nature of the development of each task.

The role of the native language is very important in the formation of a person's personality. At preschool age, a child actively learns spoken language, the formation of lexical, phonetic and grammatical aspects of speech, he masters dialogical, and then monological forms of speech.

CONCLUSION

L.S. Vygotsky came to the following conclusion: "There are all factual and theoretical grounds to assert that not only the intellectual development of a child, but also the formation of his character, emotions, and personality as a whole is directly dependent on speech" [2, p.102]. Studies of Russian psychologists and psycholinguists have proved that mastering speech does not just add something to the development of a child, but rebuilds his entire psyche, all activities.

Thus, the tasks of speech development for different authors have a similar character and are aimed at achieving a single goal - the formation of not only correct, but also good oral speech, of course, taking into account their age characteristics and capabilities.

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